

The effect of ionic strength on the liquid-liquid extraction of copper(II) from aqueous solutions by capric acid in chloroform

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Abstract : The liquid-liquid extraction of copper(II) from aqueous solution by capric acid (HL) in chloroform at 25 °C has been studied. The ionic strength effect of the aqueous phase shows that the extraction of copper(II) increases with decreasing concentration of sulfate and no effect when change the concentration of nitrate. With different ionic strengths 1, 0.5, 0.25, 0.125 and 0.1 M in the aqueous phase, Cu^{II} is extracted as the complex CuL₂(HL)₂. Sulfate complex of Cu^{II} is formed in the aqueous phase. The copper-sulfate interaction has been made in evidence by using the Debye-Hückel extended limiting law of ionic activity coefficient.

Keywords : Liquid-liquid extraction, copper(II), capric acid, ionic strength, activity coefficient.

Introduction

Liquid-liquid extraction is one of the most useful techniques for selective removal and recovery of metal ions from aqueous solutions, applied in purification processes in numerous chemical and metallurgical industries. For extraction systems of the carboxylic acids, several studies of both in fundamental and practical nature have been made on the chemical process which takes place¹⁻³.

However, the data published is not enough for the complex nature of both the organic and aqueous phases and their influence on the extraction equilibrium. From the information reported on the extraction of copper with straight chain of carboxylic acids as extractants and the work reported in⁴⁻⁷ is interesting. They deduced that the stoichiometry of the complex extracted from perchlorate medium using several carboxylic acids as extractant, corresponds to the formula dimer Cu₂L₄(HL)₂ in non-solvating solvents from n-butyric to capric acid⁵⁻¹⁵.

The effect of change of anion on the extraction of copper(II) at constant ionic strength has been studied by reference¹⁵. Copper is more easily extracted from nitrate and chloride solution than from sulfate solution. This is expected since the sulfate complexes of copper are much stronger than the corresponding chloride or nitrate complexes and this complexing results in a depression in the

extraction of copper as the anion is changed from nitrate to chloride and sulfate.

The addition of sodium sulfate decreases the extraction efficiency due to the formation of CuSO₄ ion-pair into the aqueous phase¹⁶.

In the present paper, the study of the liquid-liquid extraction of copper(II) from sulfate and nitrate media with capric acid (HL) in chloroform is carried out. Our interest in this paper is to study the effect of ionic strength of the aqueous sulfate and nitrate media on the extraction of Cu^{II} and to see if the complexes of copper could be formed in the aqueous phase using different ionic strengths 1, 0.5, 0.25, 0.125, 0.1 M.

The Debye-Hückel extended limiting law of ionic activity coefficient has been introduced in order to gain information about the copper-sulfate interaction.

Experimental

Reagents :

Capric acid (98%, PANRAC SINTESIS) was used as purchased. Copper sulfate, sodium sulfate, copper nitrate, sodium nitrate and sodium hydroxide were supplied by (Biochame). Chloroform was pre-equilibrated with aqueous solution which did not contain copper(II). The initial compositions of the phases were as follow :

Aqueous phase : $[Cu^{2+}]_j = 1.57 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (100 ppm);

$[Na_2SO_4] = 0.033, 0.04, 0.08, 0.16 \text{ and } 0.33 \text{ M}$;

$[NaNO_3] = 0.1, 0.125, 0.25, 0.5 \text{ and } 1 \text{ M}$;

Organic phase : $[HL]_{org} = 0.01, 0.02 \text{ and } 0.04 \text{ M}$ in chloroform.

Extraction and analytical procedures :

Extractions were performed on thermostated vessels at 25 °C. Equal volumes (40 mL) of both phases were contacted under magnetic stirring until the equilibrium was attained (max 20 mn) and then separated by gravity. The pH was adjusted by NaOH 0.1 M solutions of suitable compositions. The metal ion concentrations were determined in aqueous phase photometrically at 810 nm using a Philips UV-Vis SP6-36, with 1 cm glass cells was used for absorbance measurement. The metal ion concentrations in the organic phase were calculated from the difference between the metal ion concentrations in the aqueous phase before and after extraction.

Results and discussion

General treatment of extraction equilibrium of copper(II) with capric acid :

Capric acid exists as a dimer in solvents of low polarity such as toluene, benzene, chlorobenzene, dichloroethane, carbon tetrachloride alkanes⁶ and chloroform¹⁷. The extraction of copper by a dimerized capric acid $(HL)_2$, in chloroform can be represented by the general equation :

where the subscripts aq and org correspond to the aqueous and organic phases, respectively, and j, corresponds to degree of polymerization of the complex, $(HL)_2$ is extractant in dimeric form, n is cationic charge, and m is the number of monomeric acids contained in the complex. The extraction constant can be written as the following expression :

$$K_{ex} = \frac{[(ML_n(HL)_m)_j]_{org} [H^+]^{nj}}{[M^{n+}]^j_{aq} [(HL)_2]^{j(n+m)/2}_{org}} \quad (2)$$

The distribution coefficient D_M of the metal between the organic and aqueous phases may be expressed as follows :

$$D_M = \frac{C_{M_{org}}}{C_{M_{aq}}} = \sum_j \sum_m \frac{j[ML_n(HL)_m]_{org}}{[M^{n+}] \alpha_M} = \sum_j \sum_m \left(j K_{ex} [M^{n+}]^{(j-1)}_{aq} \alpha_M^{-1} [(HL)_2]^{j(n+m)/2}_{org} [H^+]^{-nj} \right) \quad (3)$$

where $C_{M_{org}}$, $C_{M_{aq}}$ and M_{index} are the total concentrations of the metal in the organic and aqueous phases, and the side reaction coefficient allows metal complication in the aqueous phase, respectively. If only $(ML_n(HL)_m)_j$ is responsible for the extraction system, eq. (4) is derived from eq. (3) as follows :

$$\log D_M = (j - 1) \log [M^{n+}]_{aq} + j \frac{n+m}{2} \log [(HL)_2]_{org} + (nj)pH - \log \alpha_M + \log j + \log K_{ex} \quad (4)$$

the slope moved a predetermined capric acid concentration in the organic phase, the relationship

$\log D_M + \log [M^{n+}]_{aq} = f(\log [M^{n+}]_{aq} + npH)$ (5) should give a straight line of slope j. On the other hand, at a predetermined metal concentration in the aqueous phase, the relationship

$$\log D_M - (j - 1) \log [M^{n+}]_{aq} - (nj)pH = f(\log [(HL)_2]) \quad (6)$$

should yield a straight line of slope $j \frac{n+m}{2}$ which intersects the axis at $(\log K_{ex} + \log \alpha_M + \log j)$.

Eq. (4) shows that the function $\log D_M = f(pH)$ at a constant $[(HL)_2]_{org}$ which should yield a straight line with a slope of n only when j and α_M are equal to unity.

Extraction of copper(II) with capric acid from sulfate and nitrate media at constant ionic strength :

The stoichiometries of the extracted species were determined by analyzing the experimental data. Conventional slope analysis was further used.

The experimental results are arranged according to

eq. (4). Figs. 1 and 2 shows the results obtained for extraction of copper(II) with solutions of various capric acid concentrations.

The degree of extraction of Cu^{II} increases with the increase in pH and capric acid concentration. Plots of $\log D_M$ versus pH for various concentration of capric acid are straight lines with slope equal to 2 ($n = 2$). This suggests full neutralization of copper(II) valence leading to the release of two protons as given by eq. (7). The data in Figs. 1 and 2 also reveal no dependence of copper distribution upon the aqueous copper concentration; thereby, the confirmer the monomeric nature of the extracted complex ($j = 1, \alpha_{\text{Cu}} = 1$).

Under these experimental conditions, the concentration of metal in organic phase is negligible compared to the concentration of extractant; therefore, concentration of dimer was calculated as $[(\text{HL})_2] = [\text{HL}]/2$.

According to eq. (4), the number of capric acid molecules involved in the monomeric species can be determined from the slope of plots of $\log D_M$ against $\log [(\text{HL})_2]_{\text{org}}$ at constant pH. Plots of $\log D_M$ versus $\log [(\text{HL})_2]_{\text{org}}$ at constant pH were also linear with a slope of $(2 + m)/2 = 2$, i.e. $m = 2$, as shown in Figs. 3 and 4. This suggests that two molecules of dimeric capric acid take part in the extraction of one ion of copper. This means that only $\text{CuL}_2(\text{HL})_2$ is extracted into chloroform. The same type of extracted species was reported for the extraction of copper(II) with capric acid in cyclopentyl acetic acid and α -bromostearic acid in benzene^{18,19}.

Fig. 1. Effect of pH on the extraction of copper(II) with capric acid in chloroform at 25 °C, $[\text{Na}_2\text{SO}_4] = 0.33 \text{ M}$.

Fig. 2. Effect of pH on the extraction of copper(II) with capric acid in chloroform at 25 °C, $[\text{NaNO}_3] = 1 \text{ M}$.

Fig. 3. Determination of the number of capric acid involved in extracted complex at constant pH, $[Na_2SO_4] = 0.33 M$.

Therefore the logarithmic value of K_{ex} of copper(II) can be calculated for each experimental point ($\log K_{ex,SO_4^{2-}} = -7.19$, $\log K_{ex,NO_3^-} = -6.08$).

Extraction of copper(II) with capric acid from sulfate and nitrate media for various ionic strengths :

Figs. 5 and 6 represent plots of $\log D_M$ versus pH obtained during the extraction of copper(II) at various ionic strengths 0.1, 0.125, 0.25, 0.5 and 1 M. As it is shown, on these figures, the extraction of Cu^{II} from sulfate medium increases when the ionic strength decreases; therefore, the extraction from nitrate medium is independent of the ionic strength.

The activity coefficient (γ) may be introduced as a useful parameter to explain the effect of the ionic strength upon the liquid-liquid extraction of copper(II) from sulfate medium into chloroform.

The extraction process may be described by the fol-

Fig. 4. Determination of the number of capric acid involved in extracted complex at constant pH, $[NaNO_3] = 1 M$.

lowing equilibrium :

The extraction constant K_{ex} , describing this process, may be expressed in terms of the activity coefficients, i.e.,

$$K_{ex} = \frac{[CuL_2(HL)_2]_{org} [H^+]^2 \gamma_{CuL_2(HL)_2} \gamma_{H^+}^2}{[Cu^{2+}] [(HL)_2]_{org}^2 \gamma_{Cu^{2+}} \gamma_{(HL)_2,org}^2} \quad (9)$$

Therefore; the logarithmic values of D_{Cu} can be deduced :

$$\log D_{Cu} = \log K_{ex} + 2 \log [(HL)_2]_{org} + 2pH + \log \frac{\gamma_{(HL)_2,org}^2}{\gamma_{CuL_2(HL)_2,org}} + \log \frac{\gamma_{Cu^{2+}}}{\gamma_{H^+}^2} \quad (10)$$

$\log \frac{\gamma_{(HL)_2,org}^2}{\gamma_{CuL_2(HL)_2,org}}$ of the organic phase does not vary because it is independent of the ionic strength of the aque-

Fig. 5. Ionic strength effect on the Cu^{2+} extraction with capric acid $[(\text{HL})_2] = 0.005 \text{ M}$ in chloroform from sulfate medium.

Fig. 6. Ionic strength effect on the Cu^{2+} extraction with capric acid $[(\text{HL})_2] = 0.005 \text{ M}$ in chloroform from nitrate medium.

ous phase. Hence, at constant pH the values of $\log D_{\text{Cu}}$

depends upon $\log \frac{\gamma_{\text{Cu}^{2+}}}{\gamma_{\text{H}^+}^2}$.

The ionic activity coefficients can be determined using the Debye-Hückel extended limiting law by taking into account the size of the ions²⁰.

$$-\log \gamma_A = \frac{A_m z_A^2 I_m^{1/2}}{1 + B_m a_i I_m^{1/2}} \quad (11)$$

where, on the molality scale, the constants A_m and B_m are defined by

$$A_m = \frac{(2\pi N d_0)^{1/2}}{(1000)^{1/2}} \frac{e^3}{2,3026(kTD)^{3/2}} \quad (12)$$

and

$$B_m = \frac{(8\pi N d_0)^{1/2}}{(1000)^{1/2}} \frac{e}{(kTD)^{1/2}} \quad (13)$$

In the formulae (12) and (13), e , N , d_0 , k , T , D and Z_A represent the magnitude of the electron charge, the Avogadro constant, the density of the solvent, the Boltzmann constant, the absolute temperature, the dielectric constant of the solvent and the valency of the cation, respectively.

Since, in eq. (11), the ionic size (a_i) is not clearly defined^{20,21}, it has been introduced as the radius of hydrated cation. The values of the hydrated radii ($a_i = r_H$) used for the tabulation of the ionic activity coefficient values of Cu^{2+} and H_3O^+ are taken from²². The calculated values of these ionic activity coefficients are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. The calculated values of the ionic activity coefficient of Cu^{2+} and H^+ at 25 °C

I	γ_{H^+}	$\gamma_{\text{Cu}^{2+}}$	$\log \frac{\gamma_{\text{Cu}^{2+}}}{\gamma_{\text{H}^+}}$
1	0.7439	0.2067	-0.428
0.5	0.7650	0.2506	-0.396
0.2	0.7895	0.3072	-0.307
0.1	0.8166	0.3765	-0.248
0.1	0.8257	0.4011	-0.230

As it is shown in Table 1, $\log \left(\frac{\gamma_{\text{Cu}^{2+}}}{\gamma_{\text{H}^+}^2} \right)$ decreases with increasing values of the ionic strength and, therefore, $\log D_{\text{C}}$ decreases according to eq. (10). This result agrees satisfactorily with experimental values shown in Fig. 7.

In addition, $\Delta \log D_{\text{Cu}}$ between two different ionic strengths for copper(II) are deduced graphically from Fig. 7. Their values are reported along with those of $\Delta \log$

$\left(\frac{\gamma_{\text{Cu}^{2+}}}{\gamma_{\text{H}^+}^2} \right)$ in Table 2.

It is noticed in Table 2 that values of $\log D_{\text{Cu}}$ are

always different from those of $\Delta \log \left(\frac{\gamma_{\text{Cu}^{2+}}}{\gamma_{\text{H}^+}^2} \right)$. This difference may be due to the fact that the $\text{Cu}^{2+}-\text{SO}_4^{2-}$ interaction has not been taken into account, i.e. ($a_i = r_{\text{H}}$) during the calculation of the ionic activity coefficients using the extended Debye-Hückel limiting law eq. (11).

Table 2. Comparison between values of

Ionic strength	$\Delta \log \left(\frac{\gamma_{\text{Cu}^{2+}}}{\gamma_{\text{H}^+}^2} \right)$ and $\Delta \log D_{\text{Cu}}$	
	$\Delta \log D_{\text{Cu}}$	$\Delta \log \left(\frac{\gamma_{\text{Cu}^{2+}}}{\gamma_{\text{H}^+}^2} \right)$
0.1→0.5	0.423	0.166
0.5→1.0	0.356	0.032
0.1→1	0.779	0.198

Fig. 7. Cu^{2+} extraction with capric acid $[(\text{HL})_2] = 0.005 \text{ M}$ in chloroform from sulfate medium and nitrate aqueous media ($I = 1 \text{ M}$).

The curves illustrated by Fig. 7 could correspond with the formation of the complexes CuSO_4 not extractable, which could reduce the concentration of Cu^{2+} ; thus, it could decrease their extraction.

In the experimental conditions, this hypothesis becomes valid when the interaction constant of $\text{Cu}^{2+}-\text{SO}_4^{2-}$ is taken into account in eq. (14).

The interaction constant value of $\text{Cu}^{2+}-\text{SO}_4^{2-}$ is equal to 1.11. It was determined by making the difference between the extraction constants of copper(II) in sulfate $\log K_{\text{ex},\text{SO}_4^{2-}} = -7.19$ and nitrate aqueous media $\log K_{\text{ex},\text{NO}_3^-} = -6.08$.

Conclusion

The complexes extracted in the organic phase have $\text{CuL}_2(\text{HL})_2$ stoichiometries in the sulfate and nitrate me-

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dia, in accordance with balances of extraction :

These results give evidence of the fact that copper is more readily extracted from nitrate than sulfate media, as shown by the lower values of extraction constants from sulfate solutions. Moreover, it is observed that this effect is strengthened when the sulfate ion concentration increases. The copper(II) extraction, was greatly depressed in the presence of sulfate ions.

The addition of sodium sulfate decreases the extraction efficiency, due to the formation of CuSO_4 ion-pair into the aqueous phase.

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